

**THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH BY
VOCABULARY**

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Annotation:

The growing interest in many parts of the world in Modern Methods of Teaching English brings with it the question of how it should be done – how curriculum, subject, matter, and methodology should differ from the familiar norms developed in the past. A lot has been written on traditional teaching English, and until recently, the demand for the information on modern methods of teaching English has been limited. As well as opportunities in foreign partnership helps to develop it.

Key words:

Methodology, curriculum, subject, matter, speech activity, traditional teaching English, vocabulary, listening, speaking, reading ,writing, magazines, newspapers

Nowadays, teachers take into consideration students' demands for watching real movie stories together with reading books, magazines and newspapers. Because, as it is known not only printed materials can serve as a great source of teaching but also songs and movies play a key role in learning foreign languages. The importance of teaching by vocabulary. Vocabulary is one of the aspects of the language to be taught in the institutes. In addition to learn new vocabulary, learner need to able to use strategies to cope with unknown vocabulary met in listening or reading text, to make up for gaps in productive vocabulary in speaking and writing to gain fluency in using known vocabulary and to learn new words in isolation.

Vocabulary learning is not on end in itself. A rich vocabulary makes to perform the skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing easier. By the type of teaching in traditional style is divided into several aspects such as speaking,

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analytic reading, reading at home, practice grammar, practical phonetics. As a result, 3-4 teachers teach students in variety styles and as a result the connection of aspects is not provided. Some students learn grammar well, but in speech they meet difficulties to pronounce words. On this way we meet some questions. Maybe it is right, but in the course all aspects of teaching by new style are carrying out parallel. Moreover, there are some methods to improve learning foreign language. Lessons are fully taught in English language based on all experiences, which are needed for lessons. That is to say students begin to understand by reading, by listening, practice of writing, improve speech and others. Students are become focal point of lessons, not teachers. The teacher only helps student to get knowledge. In this way the possibility of self-studying is got well. When lessons aren't traditional, tasks are divided into couple or small group of students due to the type of it, students work in groups or individually.

English communication skill teachers must be innovative, creative and resourceful with thorough knowledge of the subject and adopt new techniques to change social economic status of our country. Whatever may be the methods and approaches, the most pragmatic and the desirable thing seems to explore the possibility of using the under used and valuable materials which will definitely facilitate the learning and teaching of language skills. We need to have interactive teaching and this changing role of education is inevitable with the introduction of multimedia technology and the spawning of a technologically-savvy generation of youths¹.

All over the world, educational institutions implementing new ideas, methods, and technology based innovations to enhance the students' knowledge in the sphere of English. Basically, teaching must include two major components sending and receiving information. Ultimately, a teacher tries his best to impart knowledge as the way he understood it. The use of innovative methods in educational institutions has the potential not only to improve education, but also to empower

people, strengthen governance. The biggest challenge any teacher faces is capturing the students' attention, and putting across ideas in such a way that it stays with them long after they have left the classroom. For this to happen, classroom experience should be redefined and innovative ideas that make teaching learning methods more effective should be implemented. Nowadays many books and articles are written to attract attention to this point. In planning curricular and methods it has been suggested that an understanding of students and their needs, interest, abilities, likes, dislikes, and developmental status should take precedence over other considerations. For instance: Dialogical speech – in this way students have a talk each other by creative approach. “Modern methodology of teaching English puts speaking in Dialogues in the first place for developing speaking skills. These skills can be trained with various teaching aids, including texts of fiction. Such dialogues give an opportunity to avoid traditional rendering of the texts and turn them into living English speech”. More than that, all the vocabulary is remembered much better. In dialogues, students train in fluency, quick reaction, acting skills and, of course, grammatical correctness. Student reads the text himself and tells the meaning. Reading is interactive.

Reading short stories, novels and other literary works written by famous Uzbek, English and American writers is very important in language learning. As a teacher of English you may apply a variety of reading strategies, analyze literary elements use a variety of strategies to read unfamiliar words and build vocabulary, prepare, organize, and present literary interpretations. Understanding by listening – by these way students can improve speech skills. Listening is a receptive form of speech activity. Comprehension of speech while listening mainly based on auditory feelings. By perceiving, reproduce what we hear, in the form of inwardly speech. Listening comprehension is impossible without working of speech motor analyzer. Of course internal speaking requires ability to speak in this language. Understanding of sounding speech, in the moment of comprehension, is

accompanied by intellectual activity, which includes recognizing of speech means and interpretation of the content. Learning English through the watching movies.

For instance, at the beginning of lesson teacher makes plan and shares news with students. Each student participates in this plan and shares news with each other's. As a result, mutual exchanging of knowledge is appeared and all students get to know the theme. Some exercises are done by couple or group of students. For working in the group students are given such tasks: organize debates, debate the theme with playing roles, and work with high techs. To work in couple they are given dialogues, grammar materials, and also reading. By these methods we can make all students to participate in lesson and teacher can help every student due to his or her demands. By using modern pedagogical and technological methods, and by the way introducing leading styles of teaching, teach growing generations, the system of speaking easily in these languages can be developed fully. As well as opportunities in foreign partnership helps to develop it. Known to us, using innovations and new pedagogical technologies are resulting well. Sometimes using same styles in teaching language may let go down interests of student to language. We advise some types of teaching in use, not to go down interest to foreign language.

To conclude it should be noted that, the teacher of 21 century should shed traditional concepts and techniques of classroom teaching and should adopt the recent and innovative teaching techniques.

The list of used literature:

1. Brown, H. Douglas. Principles of Language Learning and Teaching. 4th edition. San Francisco State University: Longman, 2000.
2. Cooper, L. Robert, Joshua A. Fishman. "A Study of Language Attitudes." In J.A. Fishman, R.L. Cooper, Conrad A.W. The Spread of English.
3. Crystal, D. English as a Global Language. 2nd edition. New York: CUP

2013

4. Richard J. "Conversational Competence through Role Play Activities", *RELC Journal* 16 (1), 1985, p. 82-100.

5. Richards, J.C., Rodgers T.S. *Approaches and methods in language teaching*. 2nd ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001. P. 236.

6. Saidova Z.U. Teaching English language as a foreign language by interactive methods // *Наука и образование сегодня*. – 2019. – №. 11 (46).

7. Saloydinova N. S. Etymology of Uzbek and English architecture-construction terminology // *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 1013-1017.